

Use transformative agreements as a way out of the capitalistic economic model in academic publishing?

I had a dream. That scholarly publishing escapes from big business and becomes again part of common good.

It is such an emphatic and idealist sentence. All things considered, though, it is not just the leftist opinion of old idealist librarians. A [recent transformative agreement between ACM and the University of California \(UC\)](#) includes a completely novel clause that inspires me some reflections on the current purpose of this new kind of agreements and what they may become in the future.

[Transformative agreements gathered and commented by ESAC](#) (Efficiency and Standards for Article Charges) show a diversity of approaches and unequal clauses and guaranties, mainly depending on parties involved in the negotiations: more or less well-endowed consortia and big commercial or smaller society publishers. Such inequalities are quite normal, as we are standing on the verge of a new era of agreements for accessing and publishing scientific knowledge, all issues are not clear yet. [Recent updates](#) brought by the CoalitionS to the Plan S about the definition and eligibility criteria for transformative journals reveal the extent of remaining uncertainties.

Financial and ethical sustainability seems to be one of the most challenging issues. “Sustainable for whom?” asked Lisa Janicke Hinchliffe in [her last article](#). The first answer coming to mind was: for all professionals having skills essential to the scholarly publishing industry. For scholars who produce and review scientific knowledge ; for funders, academic institutions and their libraries who finance research and publication of search results ; for publishers who maintain reliable infrastructures for peer-review and dissemination. Among these stakeholders, the most important capital and human investment comes from public resources. Many professionals involved in scholarly publishing matters acknowledge that the object of this chain, research outputs, should belong? to common good, and that larges amount of public money are currently lost in the huge profit margins big commercial publishers make. So, the answer could be: sustainable for main investors in first place.

That’s why a transition to Open Access seems to be the best way to render unto Caesar the things that are Caesar’s. Hybrid and Gold Open Access are the preferred road in Plan S, a complete APC model seems to be the final goal of the current transitional agreements. But [limits](#) have already been highlighted, and many questions already arise regarding the sustainability, especially financial, of this model. Here follows a non-exhaustive overview:

- Doesn’t it reinforce a commercial system for disseminating publicly funded research?
- What are the guaranties regarding transformative journals? How is the timing of the transition to a full Open Access model to be controlled?
- How? Will validation activities requested from libraries be supported?
- Which guaranties do we have regarding cost neutrality and APCs’ possible increase?
- Will institutional funding be large enough to afford the costs of full Open Access licenses?
- [Will consortia be able to devise a cost-sharing model satisfying all members?](#)
- Will independent researchers be able to afford publication costs?
- Will books, textbooks, databases, standards, etc. eventually be part of the transition to Open Access?

The issue raised in the first question above seems to me one of the most important and almost all the others ensue from it.

To address this issue, there already have been some [attempts to propose alternatives](#). But as mentioned at the beginning, a radically new approach can be found on the [page 12 of the impressive agreement](#) signed by ACM and the University of California (UC). [ESAC comments](#): “The model reflects an unusually close collaboration among universities and a scholarly society in co-creating an open access business model”.

Indeed, for the first time in an agreement between academic libraries and publishers, the page 12 “Schedule C” introduces a consortium's right to inspect the use of a part (percentage) of a publisher's profits:

“The following is a menu of services that are focused on facilitating the transition of ACM’s scholarly peer reviewed publication program to an Open Access Model. In the initial years of the transition to Open Access publication, ACM agrees to allocate 20% of the annual fees generated from ACM OPEN from Tier 1-5 Institutions in recognition of the fact that in the initial years of the transition there is likely to be a surplus generated by ACM OPEN. The University shall indicate upon signing the Agreement which of the services listed below the 20% allocation shall be utilized for”

This paragraph implies more than a fair compensation for over-estimated publish&read licensing costs during the first years. It lets the consortium keep an eye on how ACM manages financing flows, and the consortium’s involvement in decisions concerning the re-investment of public money injected into this pilot project. It appears as a first step towards a kind of membership model that radically changes the transformative goals.

ACM is a non-profit structure, including its publishing activity. The main concern of ACM with this activity is to cover its costs. Which is of course not the case of many commercial publishers, who need to generate profits funded by public institutions. [56 years after the IPO of Pergamon Press](#), and after Elsevier, [Springer also ended up getting there last March](#). Everyone has their opinion on the origins of the current situation of the scientific publishing ecosystem, and there are indeed [multiple factors](#). But the fact remains that today science is, in part, disseminated by "Private Limited Companies", "Domestic Profit Corporations", "Limited Liability Companies", etc. whose interests depart quite significantly from transparency and common good. The problem is not so much that a form of for-profit scientific publishing exists – it has existed for at least two centuries – but that, having become the most widespread, it has increased the opacity around costs publishing activity, fostering the growth of the disproportion between the profits generated and the service provided. The transition to Open Access could then be an opportunity for a Copernican revolution, it could lead public actors to have a say and impose limits on the commercial exploitation of the dissemination of public research. It is now time to close the Pandora box opened in the 1950s.

Libraries could wait for ages for a cultural change happens in the commercial publishers’ working habits. But this clause suggests a legislative approach. And it could be the first example of a long list of contractual measures encouraging a progressive transition to partnership and to reducing the profit margin scholarly publishing activities can generate. One could imagine further commitments from commercial publishers in future agreements. For example transparency on the use of incoming financial flows from institutions and profits made with public money, transparency on real costs of publishing, transparency on what profits are invested in, commitments to exit the stock market.

There still remains a long way to achieve a sustainable membership model between libraries consortia and different publishers, from small learned societies or non-profit organizations, to major commercial players who have their hands on a lucrative market and keep their business opaque. Nevertheless, the ACM example could be the harbinger of a new generation of transformative agreements: getting around a table to address together the [“funding challenge”](#) with transparency on professional practices from both sides. In the end, it could increase the confidence in a possible change of relationships between all stakeholders in the scholarly publishing chain: from a vendor-client relationship to a real partnership with common interests.

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